

Response to ‘Comments about minimum required information’:

A CRediT statement and a funding statement were added before the ‘Acknowledgement’. Also, line numbering was added.

Response to ‘1. Hook and focus’:

The Introduction was revised to better ‘hook’ the reader.

Response to ‘2. Strength of argument’:

Some references were added, and the manuscript was restructured following the suggestions, e.g. by introducing (sub-)headings.

Response to ‘3. Reader engagement’:

‘Data granularity’ and ‘data representativity’ and ‘interoperability’ were defined as ‘data ‘...granularity (i.e. the level of detail in a data structure) and representativity (i.e. the extent to which a dataset reflects the population/phenomena it aims to represent),...’.

Response to ‘Length, language, structuring’:

The bullet list from the panel discussion was transformed into free text and revised to connect them better and in a more logical order.

(Sub-)headings were added to improve the structure.

The Introduction/Abstract was revised, making it more concise and trying to present a better ‘hook’.